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**HEPATOPROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF SWEET BASIL
(*OCIMUM BASILICUM* L.) EXTRACT IN ACETAMINOPHEN-INDUCED
HEPATOTOXICITY IN RATS**

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The liver is the center of the metabolic transformation of drugs and other xenobiotics and detoxifying processes. The aqueous and ethanolic extract of *Ocimum basilicum* had a protective effect against liver damage. Observed effects were mediated by significant radical scavenging activity, therefore suppressing free radical-mediated lipid peroxidation leading to the accumulation of lipid-derived oxidation products that cause liver injury. The aim of this study was to evaluate the *in vivo* effects of basil extract pre-treatment on liver function in acetaminophen-induced liver injury.

Effects of basil extract on biochemical markers of liver injury were determined in an *in vivo* model of acetaminophen-induced liver injury in 24 Wistar rats. To estimate the extent of liver damage after acetaminophen administration, the following parameters were determined in serum: aspartate aminotransferase activity (AST), alanine aminotransferase activity (ALT), direct bilirubin level.

Administration of acetaminophen resulted in a statistically significant difference in ALT and AST levels in comparison to the control group ($p < 0.01$), confirming the onset of liver injury. The ALT values in the group pre-treated with basil extract prior to acetaminophen administration were lower than those treated with saline and acetaminophen, but without statistical significance. On the other hand, levels of AST were statistically significantly lower in the basil pre-treated acetaminophen group in comparison to the group treated with saline and acetaminophen ($p < 0.01$). Seven-day pre-treatment with aqueous basil extract prevented the increase in the direct bilirubin levels, implying preserved excretory liver function.

The present study demonstrated the significant hepatoprotective potential of aqueous basil extract in a model of acetaminophen induced liver injury. Hepatoprotective effects were apparent through the decreasing serum activity of liver transferase enzymes as well as preserved excretory liver function in animals pre-treated with basil extract.

Keywords: basil, acute liver injury, laboratory animals, acetaminophen.